

DIPOLE MOMENTS OF ANACARDIC ACID AND CARDOL

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Dielectric constants of raw cashew shell liquid extracted from unroasted cashew shells have been investigated. The constituents of cashew shell liquid, anacardic acid and cardol, have been separated and their dielectric constants and dipole moments determined. The molecular structures of anacardic acid and cardol have been corroborated by the measurement of physical properties.

Krishnamurthy and Iyengar (*Indian J Phys.*, 1950, 24, 23) undertook for the first time an investigation of the dielectric properties of an oil which was not a glyceride but essentially a mixture of phenolic bodies. They took commercial samples of cashew shell liquids available in India for such a study and showed how the dielectric properties of the different samples of shell liquids varied with source, method of extraction and the extent of initial processing.

In the present investigation, dielectric constants of raw shell liquid obtained from unroasted cashew shells have been measured. The raw shell liquid has been separated into its constituents, anacardic acid and cardol, and their dipole moments have been calculated using the D.C.M. equation and the new equation put forth by Jatkar *et al.* (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1946, 28A, Part II). The molecular structures of these substances have been corroborated by the measurement of dielectric properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Extraction of Raw Cashew shell Liquid.—Unroasted cashew shells from Trivandrum were cut to small pieces and the pieces were extracted with solvents like benzene, alcohol and acetone in a glass Soxhlet apparatus. The benzene extracted liquid was very clear while the other liquids were slightly turbid in spite of repeated filtrations under vacuum. The liquids were then dried in vacuum for 8 hours (to remove last traces of moisture).

Separation of the Constituents.—The alcohol-extracted raw shell liquid (300 g.) was dissolved in 700 c.c. of petrol (b.p. 60°-80°). The solution was filtered through vegetable charcoal. The solvent was distilled off and the clear raw shell liquid was obtained. The liquid (100 g.) was dissolved in alcohol and an excess of freshly precipitated lead hydroxide was added. The lead salt (liberated) was dried and washed with alcohol to free it from cardol. The lead salt was dissolved in ether and 1:1 hydrochloric acid was added to decompose the lead salt. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for about an hour. The anacardic acid separated as a brown supernatant oil. The solution of anacardic acid in ether was washed with water and then the solvent was distilled off under vacuum. The acid was again dissolved in alcohol and reprecipitated with lead hydroxide. Anacardic acid was obtained as needle-shaped crystals when chilled in ice, m.p. 24-25°. [Wasserman and Dawson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3675) report its melting point as 25-26°. The room temperature itself was about 27° and it was difficult to crystallise the acid.] The following table gives the constants of anacardic acid isolated.

TABLE I

Constants.	Author.	*Pillay.
Refractive index (30°)	1.519	1.5163
Density (30°)	1.007	1.0052
Melting point	24-26°	23-25°

*this *Journal*, 1935, 12, 226.

The alcoholic solution of cardol was agitated with lead hydroxide and then filtered through vegetable carbon. The alcohol was evaporated and cardol was obtained in the form of a viscous brown oil.

Purification of Solvents for Dielectric Measurements.—Benzene was shaken with concentrated sulphuric acid to free it from thiophene. It was washed free of acid, dried and then frozen in ice. The frozen benzene was distilled over phosphorus pentoxide twice and it had a constant boiling point of 77.5°/680 mm.

Dioxane was dried over sodium and distilled and the distillate had a constant boiling point of 97.5°/680 mm.

Apparatus.—A very simple circuit similar to the one used by Nagamani and Jatkar (*Qrt. J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1942, 3, 81), was used for the measurement of capacities.

Dielectric constant and density of cardol and anacardic acid were measured both in the liquid state and in solutions. Dipole moments were calculated by applying the new equation (Jatkar *et. al.*, *loc. cit.*):

$$P = (\epsilon - 1)M/D; \quad P_E = (n^2 - 1)M/D$$

and

$$P - P_E = \frac{4\pi N\mu^2}{KT} \quad \text{for pure liquids;}$$

$$P_{1,2} = \frac{(\epsilon_{1,2} - 1)}{d_{1,2}} = p_1 w_1 + p_2 w_2 \quad \text{and}$$

and

$$P_2 = p_2 M_2 \quad \text{and} \quad P_2 - P_E = \frac{4\pi N\mu^2}{KT} \quad \text{for solutions.}$$

The moments were also calculated using the Debye-Clausius-Mosotti equation for the dilute solutions of the compounds in non-polar solvents.

$$P_{1,2} = \frac{(\epsilon_{1,2} - 1)}{(\epsilon_{1,2} + 2)} \times \frac{1}{d_{1,2}} = p_1 w_1 + p_2 w_2$$

$$P_2 = p_2 M_2;$$

$$P_2 - P_E + \frac{4\pi N\mu^2}{9KT}$$

Physical properties of raw cashew shell liquid extracted from unroasted shells are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Raw shell liquid.	Ref. index. at 27.5°.	Density at		
		30°.	50°.	70°.
Benzene extracted	1.522-1.520	0.9786	0.9668	0.9547
Alcohol extracted	1.521-1.519	0.9747	0.9650	0.9519
Acetone extracted	1.524-1.522	0.9833	0.9744	0.9598

TABLE III

Dipole moment of anacardic acid.

t°.	w ₂	d.	P.	μ × 10 ⁻¹⁸	
				(Jatkar).	(Debye).
Pure .					
30°	...	6.56	1899	2.82	...
50°	...	7.31	2180	3.17	...
70°	...	8.03	2465	3.53	...
Solvent-dioxane					
25°	0.0000	2.24	...	(3.32)	...
	0.0586	2.62	1.025	2565	3.37
	0.1423	3.17	1.028	2600	3.39
	0.2116	3.89	1.031	1698	3.47
				Av. 3.34	
40°	0.0586	2.57	1.016	2384	3.22
	0.1423	3.10	1.013	2497	3.39
	0.2116	3.79	1.018	2606	3.45
					Av. 3.32

TABLE IV

Dipole moment of cardol.

t°.	w ₁	ε.	d.	P.	μ × 10 ⁻¹⁸	
					(Jatkar).	(Debye).
Pure.						
30°	...	4.86	0.9795	1246	2.90	...
50°	...	5.44	0.9650	1403	2.37	...
70°	...	6.05	0.9519	1560	2.63	...
Solvent-benzene						
25°	0.0000	2.27	0.8726	...	(2.12)	...
	0.2109	2.97	0.9031	1449	2.33	2.63
	0.2365	2.97	0.9057	1420	2.30	2.58
	0.4372	3.81	0.9358	1582	2.48	2.56
					Av. (2.37)	
40°	0.2109	2.84	0.8880	1399	2.33	2.60
	0.2365	2.90	0.8906	1372	2.30	2.62
	0.4372	3.71	0.9187	1545	2.50	2.62
					Av. (2.34)	

DISCUSSION

The temperature variation of the dielectric constants of the raw cashew shell liquids is shown in Table V.

TABLE V

Sample of the liquid.	Dielectric constants at				
	30°.	50°.	70°.	90°.	100°.
Benzene extracted	4.18	4.16	4.15	4.12	4.08
Alcohol extracted	4.41	4.39	4.29	4.17	4.12
Acetone extracted	4.48	4.47	4.43	4.26	4.21

The dielectric constants at 30° and 50° for the alcohol and acetone extracted samples are very nearly the same. After 50° the dielectric constant decreases gradually. The variation of the dielectric constant with temperature of the benzene-extracted liquid is very small, the dielectric constant decreasing by 0.1 (4.18 to 4.08) over a range of 70° (30°-100°). The dielectric constants have a tendency to converge at higher temperatures. The dielectric constant measurements above 100° were not possible since the liquids started frothing and became conducting. The slight differences in the behaviour of the dielectric constant with temperature of the three samples are due to the viscosity effects similar to those observed with commercial shell liquids (cf. Krishnamurthy and Iyenger, *loc. cit.*, p. 29). The commercial liquid has a higher dielectric constant. The value shows entirely different behaviour with temperature as compared with the raw shell liquid. The difference with the dielectric constant of the liquids is not surprising in view of the fact that during commercial extraction the liquid is known to decarboxylate and also to polymerize.

The dielectric constants of anacardic acid and cardol are given in Table VI.

TABLE VI

	Dielectric constants at			
	30°.	50°.	70°.	90°.
Anacardic acid	6.55	7.31	8.03	9.06
Cardol	4.86	5.44	6.05	6.32

The dielectric constants of anacardic acid and cardol show a large positive temperature coefficient in the range studied (30°-90°). It is interesting to compare the dielectric constant of sodium bicarbonate solubles of cashew shell liquid with that of anacardic acid, since the former are expected to contain a high proportion of anacardic acid (Krishnamurthy and Iyenger, *loc. cit.*). Though the dielectric constant of the bicarbonate solubles also increases with temperature (Krishnamurthy and Iyengar, *loc. cit.*), the absolute value as well as the temperature coefficient are decidedly lower than those of the anacardic acid. This may be due to the presence (in the bicarbonate solubles) of other acids of low molecular weight resulting from the decomposition of anacardic acid during the drastic thermal treatment.

Cardol, the dihydroxyphenol, has a higher dielectric constant than the bicarbonate insolubles, which are mainly composed of the monophenol, anacardol.

It is of interest to note that though anacardic acid and cardol have a high dielectric constant (4.8 to 9), the raw shell liquid, which consists mainly of these two components, has decidedly a lower value (4.1-4.5). It may be possible that in the raw liquid, molecules of cardol are contra-associated with those of anacardic acid.

The moments of anacardic acid and cardol in solvents (benzene and dioxane) have been calculated by using the new relationship (Jatkar, *Nature*, 1944, 153, 222) and also by Debye's equation (Table III and IV). μ_p is higher than μ_{new} . The moment of anacardic acid (I) is 3.3 as compared to that of *ortho*-hydroxybenzoic

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

acid (II), 2.8. It may be pointed out that the extrapolated value 2.8 is only a rough estimate, since the moment shows a variation with concentration (cf. Kulkarni, 1949, Ph.D. thesis of the University of Bombay). The moment of cardol (III) is 2.3. This can be compared to resorcinol (IV) which has a moment of 1.7 in benzene and 2 in dioxane (Kulkarni, *loc. cit.*).

The fact that the moment of anacardic acid and that of *ortho*-hydroxybenzoic acid are practically of the same value substantiates the chemical evidence that the structure of anacardic acid is similar to *ortho*-hydroxybenzoic acid. The moment of cardol compares with that of resorcinol, showing thereby that the structure of cardol is similar to resorcinol. Thus the structure of cardol shown by chemical evidence is corroborated by the physical measurement of dielectric property. The slight increase in the moments of anacardic acid and cardol over those of *ortho*-hydroxybenzoic acid and resorcinol may be respectively due to $C_{15}H_{27}$ side-chain.

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